

One Way Analysis of Variance

vendredi, août 13, 2021, 12:43:08

Data source: Data 1 in PESONotebook2.JNB

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk): Failed (P < 0,050)

Equal Variance Test (Brown-Forsythe): Passed (P = 0,764)

Group Name	N	Missing	Mean	Std Dev	SEM
Control	10	0	237,650	21,187	6,700
HI	109	0	229,972	125,053	11,978
HG	12	0	252,158	29,219	8,435

Source of Variation	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Between Groups	2	5597,877	2798,939	0,210	0,810
Residual	128	1702371,612	13299,778		
Total	130	1707969,489			

The differences in the mean values among the treatment groups are not great enough to exclude the possibility that the difference is due to random sampling variability; there is not a statistically significant difference (P = 0,810).

Power of performed test with alpha = 0,050: --